

Direct Synthesis of Ferrocenyl Alcohols from Aldehydes and Ferrocene catalysed by Lewis Acid

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Manuscript received 16 December 1993, revised 19 October 1994, accepted 12 January 1995

The number of reports dealing with the chemistry of ferrocene is staggering. Ferrocenyl alcohol has been most successfully prepared from (dimethylamino)-methylferrocene in three steps¹. Recently, the reaction of ferrocene with aldehydes and ketones in strongly acidic medium to produce ferrocenyl alcohols and olefines derived from these alcohols has been described², but this method only gains monosubstituted mixture containing alcohol and olefine, and the yield of ferrocenyl alcohol is not more than 50%.

We report here a new method of synthesis of di-substituted ferrocenyl alcohols from ferrocene and aromatic aldehydes catalysed by anhydrous aluminium chloride in mild condition.

Ar = a: C₆H₅, b: *p*-CH₃O-C₆H₅, c: *p*-F-C₆H₅, d: *o*-Cl-C₆H₅,
e: *o*-NO₂-C₆H₅

Experimental

Melting point were taken in open capillaries in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FT-5DX spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL PMX-60 instrument using TMS as internal standard and electronic spectra on a DU-7B spectrophotometer using 1,1'-dichloroethane as solvent.

1,1'-Bis(α-hydroxybenzylcyclopentadienyl)iron (1a): To a mixture of ferrocene (186 mg, 1 mmol) and benzaldehyde (265 mg, 2.5 mmol) in dichloromethane (15 ml) was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (60 mg, 0.4 mmol), and the reaction mixture

was stirred for 6 h at room temperature until tlc showed that the reaction was complete. A saturated ammonium chloride solution (10 ml) was added to the mixture, and the separated layer of dichloromethane was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then rotary-evaporated. The residue was chromatographed on a column of silica gel, eluting with 10% acetone in petroleum ether, to give pure **1a** (330 mg, 83%), m.p. 136–38° (lit.³ 136–37°).

Other compounds were prepared similarly: **1b** (81%), **1c** (89%), **1d** (84%), **1e** (86%).

The ir spectra of compounds **1a-e** revealed band at 3 400 cm⁻¹ (O–H) which is characteristic of a new O–H group formed. The cyclopentadienyl and aryl groups in all compounds showed bands around 3 100 (C–H of ring stretch), 1 450, 1 410, 1 380 and 1 340 cm⁻¹ (C–C of ring stretch), 1 100 and 1 030 cm⁻¹ (C–H of ring deformation). The ¹H nmr spectra of **1a-e** showed signals at δ4.2–4.5 (substituted cyclopentadienyl proton), 7.0–7.8 (ArH), 3.8–4.0 (CH–O–). The electronic spectral bands of **1a-e** at 230–250 and 255–280 nm are respectively attributed to π–π* transition of cyclopentadienyl and aryl groups⁴. The charge transfer transition between the cyclopentadienyl ring and iron revealed bands at 315–345 and 425–460 nm, whose absorptions are weak, because the transition belongs to forbidden transitions.

References

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